

DOI

Xodjimatova Z.H.
teacher

Russian language and literature of ASMI academic Lyceum

**METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE SCIENCE
IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS**

***Annotation:** the role of the Russian language among the " world " languages is huge as an international means of communication. Due to the entire course of socio-political, economic, scientific and technical and cultural development of mankind in the XX-XXI centuries, the Russian language is rightfully considered the world. This is explained primarily by the " international " nature of modern science and the unprecedented pace of its development.*

Nowadays, it is important that every student is fluent in Russian. In this regard, it is important to use new methods of teaching the Russian language.

***Keywords:** methodology, Russian language, didactics, linguistics, psychology. The word " method " comes from the Greek word " metodos ", which means " waymeans. Now the word is used in two senses.*

1. The set of techniques, methods, forms of work of the teacher in the teaching of any subject, i.e. art, the skill of the teacher.

2. The science that studies the possibilities and means of achieving the maximum result of the educational process, i.e. theory of teaching science.

The methodology of teaching the Russian language is an interdisciplinary science that is located at the intersection of several disciplines (pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, linguistics and social pedagogy) and determines the principles, methods, methods and content of education, as well as the laws of mastering and mastering knowledge. Skills in this discipline. The subject of the methodology of teaching the Russian language is quite extensive, and includes: the necessary language material that must be mastered by students in order to obtain language skills; the teacher's activities aimed at choosing the necessary educational material and methods of its implementation "feed" students; the teacher's activities in organizing the educational process, which includes not only providing students with the necessary educational material, but also the implementation of diagnostic methods aimed at determining the level of knowledge and skills; activities of students aimed at mastering the necessary knowledge and skills, as well as the development of skills within the framework of the studied educational subjects. In addition, understanding the topic of the methodology of teaching the Russian language also includes the expected learning result. The methodology is aimed at studying the concepts of language in the field of the Russian language (knowledge), the laws of the formation of skills and

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ КОММУНИКАЦИИ В НАУКЕ И БИЗНЕСЕ

abilities. It should be noted that the methodology differs from the didactics of pedagogy and psychology in that the

General Teaching of the Russian language studies not their laws, but specific things that are associated with a particular language material. The methodology considers the activities of the teacher and students as a process of interaction, expressed in joint activities, characterized by cooperation while maintaining the leading role of the teacher. Thus, the method of teaching the Russian language is aimed at solving practical problems, including the development of effective teaching methods and methods. The purpose and objectives of the methodology the main purpose of teaching is to determine the place of science (Russian language) in the modern educational system in accordance with the methodology, to highlight its importance and necessity for the younger generation. Within the framework of the methodology of teaching the Russian language, the solution of educational problems is carried out on the basis of the choice of the most optimal tools. it is effective in use in the classroom-lesson system. In addition, the methodology takes into account the number of strictly defined classes in the academic year, the amount of educational material approved by the program and textbooks. The methodology implies the use of all tools and teaching methods, both special and general (textbook, notebook, whiteboard, computer tools, etc.). All of them are used not separately, but in a complex. The technique is aimed at solving the following problems: 1. Why you need to learn Russian involves setting goals and objectives for learning. 2. What to teach-reveals the content of training, the validity of the developed program, the use of specific textbooks and workbooks, manuals. 3. The teaching method involves the development of teaching methodology and methods, the structure and science cycle of the lesson, teaching equipment and teaching aids. 4. Control over the appropriation of educational material-criteria for determining and evaluating the main methods of control. The content of teaching the Russian language in accordance with the teaching methodology includes: 1. The choice by the teacher of a specific scientific concept on which the entire educational process established by him in the future will be based. 2. Selection of a sufficient and necessary terminological and conceptual apparatus. 3. A clear definition of the range of knowledge, skills and qualifications that each student should acquire as a result of studying the academic discipline. It should also be noted that the methods of teaching, which are part of the teaching methodology, are aimed not only at direct teaching, but also at developing effective organizational tools and forms of Education. Currently, the methodology of teaching the Russian language is closely related to Psychology, Philosophy, Linguistics and pedagogy. Teaching the Russian language (and in general any subject) is a joint activity of teachers and students. In order for students to master the language competently, the teacher must perform certain educational (exercise) actions: explain new material, give assignments, ask questions and check the correctness of the answer, etc. Students also need to be active and perform a number of actions in the educational process:

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ КОММУНИКАЦИИ В НАУКЕ И БИЗНЕСЕ

reading the text, learning words, performing exercises, answering the teacher's questions, etc. In traditional forms of education (on-site), the actions of students are always determined and guided by the teacher. It is he who decides what students should do, at what point, in what sequence, for what purpose. And, of course, he also determines for himself what and how to do in the lesson (even outside the lesson). He directly teaches and teaches students to learn. But any teacher knows that the teaching action of the teacher does not always give the desired result. How to make the actions of the teacher the most effective? It is necessary to explain to him what methods, methods, methods to achieve the desired goal, how to combine them with each other, how to behave in the audience. In other words, we must teach him to consciously control the learning process, including in order for the educational process to give us the best results, we need to consciously organize our own educational activities. The topic of the methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language is the system of management of the educational process, i.e. a system aimed at the most effective assimilation of the Russian language by students. The teacher cannot be hard-coded once and for all, but he can and should be taught to build the educational process in such a way that it will achieve the greatest effect in any specific setting. And for this, the teacher needs to know what to consider, i.e. what factors determine the effectiveness of his actions; being able to perform these actions correctly, competently. Thus, the composition of the methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language includes: 1) factors determining the effectiveness of the educational process; 2) their systematic relationship, i.e. how these factors relate to each other, which are the main, determining and which are the secondary, acting at any moment of learning and related to certain conditions; 3) the rules by which the teacher must build educational activities. Teaching Russian, even in the absence of a language environment, is understood in Russian as teaching speech, communication and expression of thought. Thus, the methodology has its own subject of learning, which is not repeated in any science-to teach another language as a means of communication. This category contains the content of the entire educational process, defines the types of speech activities to be mastered, the levels of language proficiency that must be achieved in each of these types.

References:

1. Volkov G.N. Этнопедагогика: Учеб. для студ. сред. и высш. пед. учеб. заведений. -М.: Издательский центр "Академия", 1999.
2. Lyashenko M.S. Научно-теоретические аспекты формирования психолого-педагогической культуры у студентов в вузе: монография. -Н.Новгород: ВГИПУ, 2010.
3. Stolyarenko L.D. Основы психологии. 13-е изд. Учебное пособие/ Л.Д. Столяренко. -Ростов н/ Д: Феникс.